

WHAT ABOUT...

Spending those funds?

Put together your Open Science priorities based on your budget

£ 50,000

Create an interoperable system that automates all processes in the Open Science life cycle

Become an institution fully dedicated to and financially supporting all forms of Open Science

£ 10,000

Write Green Open Access into national law

Secondment of experts to create a national Open Platform

Abandon metrics, rankings and impact factors on an institutional level

£ 5,000

Set up an institutional Open Access fund

Sign up to a transformative agreement

Implement a Rights Retention policy

National Open Awards based on qualitative and not quantitative factors

£ 1,000

Resource your institutional repository for a year

Employ more ethics supervisors and require philosophy module of all PhDs

Host an annual community event showcasing open outputs

Train library, ethics and research staff in Open Science

Create a multidisciplinary open journal

Set up an expert task force to evaluate TAs and examine usage

£ 500

Pay one BPC

Support Open Book Futures

Review internal Open Science policies

Host OER workshops

Start an Open Peer Review community

Support academics to create and use OER and Open Textbooks

£ 100

Run OER session with academics

Support DOAJ for a year

Pay for a journal publishing system for a year

Support OpenAlex for a year

Have authorship agreements and use the CRediT taxonomy

Sign or create an Open Science statement

Pay one APC

Join CoARA